

ADVANTAGES OF PSYCHOTHERAPY

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Abstract. *The method of psychotherapy is a specific method arising from the understanding of the general principle of treatment, the nature of mental illness in a specific psychotherapy concept. In total, there are currently more than 400 main methods of independent psychotherapy. This article will cover it in detail!*

Keywords: *psychotherapy, treatment, positive effects, duration, types, advantages, duration of psychotherapy.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ПСИХОТЕРАПИИ

Аннотация. *Метод психотерапии – это специфический метод, вытекающий из понимания общего принципа лечения, характера психического заболевания в конкретной психотерапевтической концепции. Всего в настоящее время существует более 400 основных методов самостоятельной психотерапии. Эта статья расскажет об этом подробно!*

Ключевые слова: *психотерапия, лечение, положительные эффекты, продолжительность, виды, преимущества, продолжительность психотерапии.*

INTRODUCTION

Psychotherapy (psycho... and therapy) is a mental influence on the minds of mentally ill patients by means of words, politeness and creating a comfortable environment. General and special (or special) P. are distinguished. General P. is the process of the doctor's communication with the patient, in which various spiritual influences are focused on the patient's personality, to ensure his recovery, to calm him down, to prevent situations (iatrogeny) that arise due to the wrong actions of medical personnel (doctors). It is an auxiliary measure among all treatment measures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Help the client understand your problems;
2. Create an emotionally comfortable environment;
3. All methods of psychotherapeutic influence help in four main directions:
4. Remembering the reasons - hypnosis, psychoanalysis, gestalt therapy, existing therapy
5. Find useful habits and harmful ones - cognitive behavioral therapy (CCT), rational, personal psychotherapy;
6. Solving the problem is non-standard, without classical conversation - art therapy, physically oriented therapy, hypnosis;
7. Overcoming problems in a team or family or family - group, family psychotherapy, psychodrama;

Classification of psychotherapy. To date, there are three main areas of psychotherapy:

- Dynamic
- Behavior (or behavior)

- Essential humanity. They all have mechanisms of impact on the patient, but their essence - direction is not in the symptom, but in the whole person. Depending on the desired goal, practical psychotherapy can be:

- Psychotherapist training.

Theoretical courses of basic and accompanying subjects, individual therapy, psychological training, supervision and supervision of supervisors in the first years of practical activity. Such preparation requires 3-5 years and provides the basis for their certification and licensing, and requires a period of improvement that is repeated every 5 years and a fixed amount of time for their acceptance. Child and adolescent psychotherapist training represents a change and expansion of the program.

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RESULTS

Oral therapy. The task of the therapist is to provide the patient with emotional and emotional beginnings to eliminate pathological symptoms.

Effectiveness of psychotherapy Psychotherapy can treat even severe mental illness. However, unlike the treatment of many physical ailments, there are no guarantees. The fact is that the human psyche is very complex and many areas of it are poorly studied. Psychotherapeutic methods are effective, but do not always compete with complete recovery, usually only external improvement in the patient's condition can be achieved. Unfortunately, today there is a biased attitude towards psychotherapy. People who have undergone psychotherapy usually do not tell anyone about it. Many people do not seek the help of a psychotherapist, they are afraid to listen. However, there are problems that cannot be overcome by a person himself.

Insomnia, betrayal of a husband or wife, young family, nervous decorations, hysteria, phoboba problems, relieves emotional stress, fear and helps to return to normal life. With the appearance of various mental disorders (especially if this violation is constantly repeated), a person should consult a doctor. If the doctor examines the patient, prescribes psychotherapy, then treatment is not necessary and a psychotherapist should be consulted. Some psychotherapy methods are used to prevent mental illnesses, one of which is self-sufficiency. Parents and children learn to maintain peace and inner harmony through special techniques organized by family highways.

Psychotherapy is the process of influencing the psyche of a patient or a group of patients for therapeutic purposes. Why is psychotherapy used?

Psychotherapy is a process of influencing the psyche of a patient or a group of patients for therapeutic purposes (one-sided).

Psychotherapy does not affect the psyche of the patient for therapeutic purposes. For example, psychopharmacology is not psychotherapy.

The main type of psychotherapeutic effect is oral exposure. But every word is not a cure.

In some cases, psychotherapy is the main method of treatment (neuroses, alcoholism, smoking, some internal diseases, skin diseases, etc.), in other diseases it is a necessary auxiliary tool (in many internal diseases, in preparation for surgery and in severe diseases). postoperative period) obstetrics, gynecology, etc.)

The scope and methodology of psychotherapy varies depending on the age of the patient, the nature of the disease, personal characteristics, and the characteristics of the institution where the treatment is carried out.

The goal of activating psychotherapy is to mobilize the surviving aspects of the patient's personality and bring him to real-life situations, to perform the functions impaired as a result of the disease.

Today, there are more than 400 methods in this field, so we list the most used ones:

Rational psychotherapy It is one of the most effective methods of treating neurosis, based on the logical persuasion of the patient about the need to change the attitude towards oneself, the past, the future, the formed disease, therapy, prognosis, one's abilities and future prospects.

The technique of suggestion It includes many techniques and takes various forms, it is carried out both in the waking state and in hypnosis or a medical dream.

An indirect suggestion that is included as an integral part of any medical procedure.

You can do psychotherapy yourself by actively using automatic suggestion - the technique goes into a state of transition before waking up or going to bed. The suggestion is established by automatically repeating a single formula containing the main point of painful experiences. After a short training, you can use autogenic training, which the patient spends on himself.

Cognitive technique. It teaches the patient to see himself and the world in a more optimistic way by revising false conclusions. This type of therapy includes mild, moderate, anxiety disorders, OCD psychotherapy methods.

DISCUSSION

Behavioral techniques help the victim reduce anxiety in relation to certain situations and activate until the most important provocative stimulus stops the fear. The method is used as obsessive-compulsive disorders - OCD psychotherapy - panic, anxiety-phobic, dissociative-phobic disorders.

NLP - neurolinguistic programming - includes the main channels of communication (auditory, visual). Indications for use: panic and adaptive disorders, acute reaction to stressful situations, it is included in psychotherapy methods for the correction of ADHD - attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

CONCLUSIONS

The method of meditative reincarnation psychotherapy is based on meditation, and its duration does not exceed a few minutes. At the same time, negative emotions are projected beyond the present life. During the implementation of the technique, the negative potential changes to a positive one.

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